
APPENDIX

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Appendix I

immediate

A1 | METEOROLOGICAL VARIABLES

FIGURE A1 Yearly variability of climatic variables values observed at the meteorological station Reckenholz (REH) between 2009 and 2022 during the months of May to September. Rainfall corresponds to yearly sums, while other variables represent daily average values.

A2 | SOIL PROFILE DESCRIPTION IN THE MODELS

FIGURE A2 Schematic representation of the soil profile in each model. All models have homogeneous soil hydraulic properties following pedological layers.

A3 | AUXILIARY PLOTS MODEL VALIDATION

FIGURE A3 Validation of number of flowering days and development stages (DVS) of silage maize using the models SWAP, DAISY and CANDY.

FIGURE A4 Measured (grey crosses) and simulated values of cumulative actual evapotranspiration of silage maize in the lysimeters in the years 2015 and 2021. Solid lines represent mean values of all PTFs and shading depicts the range (minimum and maximum values) for each model.

FIGURE A5 Measured (grey crosses) and simulated cumulative values of seepage water during the period with silage maize in the lysimeters in the years 2015 and 2021. Full lines represent mean values amongst all PTFs and shading shows minimum and maximum values for each model.

FIGURE A6 Measured soil water content (grey crosses) over the dry year 2015 (panel columns) at all soil depths (panel rows) in comparison to soil water contents simulated with each of the four models. Colored full lines indicate mean values derived with all pedotransfer functions, shading indicates the full range between minimum and maximum.

FIGURE A7 Measured soil water content (grey crosses) over the wet year 2021 (panel columns) at all soil depths (panel rows) in comparison to water contents simulated with each of the four models. Colored full lines indicate mean values derived with all pedotransfer functions, shading indicates the full range between minimum and maximum.

d: cwdm

FIGURE A8 Comparison of d values for estimated aboveground biomass from all models. Blue highlighted values represent the best performing PTF for each model. Red highlighted values represent the worst performing PTF for each model. Averaged values for the years of 2015 and 2021.

FIGURE A9 Comparison of NSE values for estimated actual evapotranspiration from all models. Blue highlighted values represent the best performing PTF for each model. Red highlighted values represent the worst performing PTF for each model. Averaged values for the years of 2015 and 2021.

FIGURE A10 Comparison of NSE values for estimated seepage water by all models. Blue highlighted values represent the best performing PTF for each model. Red highlighted values represent the worst performing PTF for each model. Averaged values for the years of 2015 and 2021.

FIGURE A11 Comparison of NSE values for soil water content at 10, 30, 60 and 90 cm from all models. Blue highlighted values represent the best performing PTF for each model and depth. Red highlighted values represent the worst performing PTF for each model. Averaged values for the years of 2015 and 2021.

A4 | ANALYSIS OF MODEL STRUCTURAL DIFFERENCES

A4.1 | Leaf area index

FIGURE A12 Simulated values of leaf area index during the period with silage maize in the lysimeters in the years 2015 and 2021. Full lines represent mean values amongst all PTFs and shading shows minimum and maximum values for each model.

A4.2 | Rooting depth and root development

FIGURE A13 Simulated values of rooting depth during the period with silage maize in the lysimeters in the years 2015 and 2021. Full lines represent mean values amongst all PTFs and shading shows minimum and maximum values for each model.

A4.3 | Oxygen stress simulation by SWAP

FIGURE A14 Simulated values of transpiration reduction due to dry (Treddry) and wet (Tredwet) conditions in SWAP. Vertical ranges correspond to different PTFs.

A5 | ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE: PTF VERSUS MODEL

| Decomposing Contributions in ANOVA

The predicted contributions (\hat{y}_{PTF} , \hat{y}_{model} , and $\hat{y}_{interaction}$) in the ANOVA model are calculated as follows:

1. Main Effect of PTF (\hat{y}_{PTF}):

$$\hat{y}_{PTF_k} = \mu + \alpha_{PTF_k}$$

where:

$$\alpha_{\text{PTF}_k} = \bar{y}_{\text{PTF}_k} - \mu$$

Here, \bar{y}_{PTF_k} is the mean of all observations for the k -th PTF level.

2. Main Effect of model (\hat{y}_{model_j}):

$$\hat{y}_{\text{model}_j} = \mu + \beta_{\text{model}_j}$$

where:

$$\beta_{\text{model}_j} = \bar{y}_{\text{model}_j} - \mu$$

Here, \bar{y}_{model_j} is the mean of all observations for the j -th model level.

3. Interaction Effect ($\hat{y}_{\text{interaction}}$):

$$\hat{y}_{\text{interaction}_{kj}} = \mu + \alpha_{\text{PTF}_k} + \beta_{\text{model}_j} + \gamma_{\text{interaction}_{kj}}$$

where:

$$\gamma_{\text{interaction}_{kj}} = \bar{y}_{\text{PTF}_k, \text{model}_j} - (\mu + \alpha_{\text{PTF}_k} + \beta_{\text{model}_j})$$

where $\bar{y}_{\text{PTF}_k, \text{model}_j}$ is the mean of all observations for the combination of k -th PTF level and j -th model level.

Complementary model combinations

FIGURE A15 Analysis of variance contribution of "PTF" versus "model" and their interactions for simulated aboveground biomass (AG biomass, Mg ha^{-1}), actual annual evaporation (mm y^{-1}), actual annual transpiration (mm y^{-1}), and annual seepage water (mm y^{-1}). The total bar size represents the range between the minimum and maximum values in all model \times PTF combinations. Arrows indicate years when silage maize was grown on the lysimeters and aboveground biomass data was available.

FIGURE A16 Analysis of variance contribution of "PTF" versus "model" and their interactions for simulated aboveground biomass (AG biomass, Mg ha^{-1}), actual annual evaporation (mm y^{-1}), actual annual transpiration (mm y^{-1}), and annual seepage water (mm y^{-1}). The total bar size represents the range between the minimum and maximum values in all model \times PTF combinations. Arrows indicate years when silage maize was grown on the lysimeters and aboveground biomass data was available.

FIGURE A17 Analysis of variance contribution of PTF versus model and interactions for the outputs in above ground biomass, yearly evapotranspiration, yearly seepage water...

FIGURE A18 Analysis of variance contribution of PTF versus model and interactions for the outputs in above ground biomass, yearly evapotranspiration, yearly seepage water...